

EFFECTS OF PSYCHOSOCIAL WORK AND MUSCULOSKELETAL DISORDERS ON CONSTRUCTION WORKERS' STRESS IN YOBE STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The paper examine the effect of psychosocial work and musculoskeletal disorders on construction workers' stress in Yobe state, where it has pointed out some work related injuries and illness that are normally fatal and some are very critical to construction workers' health. Some explanations on psychosocial were pointed out as an aspect involving psychological and social aspect such as age, education and marital history. The paper identified two purposes of the study and two research questions that posed into two hypotheses and also reviewed some literatures on the effects of psychosocial work and risk factors and it identified causes of any particular cases of Musculoskeletal Disorder (MSD) which are exceedingly difficult to identify with complete accuracy. The study concluded by revealing the data on the findings of the research on null hypothesis one which revealed that there is effects of psychosocial work on construction workers' stress in construction industry. It also revealed that risk factors on workers' stress in construction industry was identified as most common. The study recommended that: Construction industry workers should avoid any anti-social vices that will cause effects of psychosocial work like aggression and harassment or low job control that will affect workers in construction industry. It also recommended that Construction industry workers should avoid any act of risk such as ergonomic risk like high job demands, uncomfortable static position, contact stress of muscles and tendons and extreme temperature condition should be avoided to prevent the development of ergonomic risks on construction industry workers.

INTRODUCTION

In construction industries, there are some work-related injuries and illness that are normally fatal and some are very critical to construction workers' health, if allowed to persist will result in to psychosocial and economic costs Hinze, J., & Appelgate, L. L. (1991). Psychosocial was viewed by Yunuskara and Dayan (2022) as an aspect involving psychological and social aspect such as age, education, marital history among others. Other view on psychosocial by Batraw, Fitzgerald and Joiner (2022) in Gale encyclopedia of medicine is a term referring to the minds' ability to consciously or unconsciously adjust and relate the body to its social environment. Apart from direct psychosocial and economic costs which includes medical care or compensation and direct impact to construction industries like decline in productivity, some social costs like musculoskeletal disorder must be put into consideration as a consequence Leigh, J. P. (2011). This consequence has significant effect on workers' stress and Musculoskeletal Disorder (MSD) which occurs due to tremendous repetitive action by workers in construction industries.

Stress was pointed by Naddin (2017), that it is not a disease but prolonged exposure to it may reduce effectiveness at work and may cause ill-health, ranging from mild headache to severe depression. Naddin (2017), also highlighted the symptoms of stress in organizations that it can result in increased absenteeism, high staff turnover, disciplinary problems, violence and psychological harassment, reduced productivity, as well as reduced attention, mistakes and accidents. (Kwami 2025) stated that Government and public organizations encourages construction industries to adopt strategies that can reduce the prevalence of this illness like musculoskeletal disorder, this will help in reducing the risk factors of the MSD through physical work design and implementing training programs that will improve cognitive process of workers in construction industries, as a result, it will reduce mental workload and increase developmental changes

Risk is a major factor taken for granted by construction workers, Dyes, Bomsat, Maguit and Colbarn (2022) defined risk as a possibility for something bad to happen sometime in the future. They therefore added that risk includes a situation that could be dangerous or may have a bad result and risk factors are common concepts used in safety and applied ergonomics. Risk factors are some things that increase a person's chances of developing diseases, therefore, it can be considered as actions or conditions that increase the likelihood of injury to the occurrence of musculoskeletal disorder (MSD). Some common risk factors were identified by Huntsville (2019), as Age, High blood pressure, High cloistral and smoking. Therefore, biomechanical exposures include factors such as poorly designed workplaces and biomechanical exposures such as repetitive motion, high forces and deviations from neutral body alignments (Yip, 2017). All these factors when gathered will interact and affect the psychological climate in the work place like construction industries.

When considering the work place like construction industries, this risk factor can be considered as a situation that exist or created intentionally or unintentionally that could or might contribute to results contravene or against the principles or philosophy of ergonomics that could be harmful to the health and well-being of workers or users during work or after work (Pascale, So, Waldemar & William 2019). The primary symptoms of risk factors (RF) are repetition, force, awkward posture, vibration, contact stress, static loading and extreme temperature. Risk factor exposure is an early warning of progressively more serious problems -physical signs and symptoms that can lead to serious injury and long-term exposure to risk factors will reduce the quality of life Marras, W. S., & Karwowski, W. (2006). Organizations and individuals can become better informed to reduce injury risk by being aware of risk factors, becoming skilled in recognizing and categorizing these factors, and examining

options to reduce the frequency or duration of exposure to the risk factors. Reducing exposure to risk factors should make the task smoother and more predictable in its outcome.

Although the causes of any particular cases of Musculoskeletal Disorder (MSD) are exceedingly difficult to identify with complete accuracy, certain risk factors are typically discussed in the field of ergonomic studies. Musculoskeletal Disorder (MSD) is a condition or disorder that involves the muscles, nerves, tendons, ligaments, joints, cartilage, or spinal discs Punnett, L., & Wegman, D. H. (2004). These disorders are not typically the result of a distinctive, singular event, but are more gradual in their development. Some work activities can strain the bodies of workers during work most especially construction industries workers. This may lead to injuries to the muscles, tendons, ligaments and joints. This type of injury is called a musculoskeletal injury (MSI). Parts of the job that may strain workers' bodies or increase the Risk of Injury (MSI) are called risk factors, (Jaffar, Abdul Tharim, Mohd-Kamar, Lop & Jaffar, 2019). In addressing any ergonomic issue, it would be a mistake to focus solely on the workplace. The major work-related risk factors are repetitive work, exerting a force, awkward and static postures, contact stress or pressure. The factors that contribute to the risk of Musculoskeletal Injury (MSI) are called risk factors. Workers may not always be able to identify all the risk factors in a task. However, it is important for workers to recognize situations when they are at higher risk. Furthermore, not every person exposed to any or all of these risk factors will develop a CTD or MSD.

Various studies were conducted on Automobile workers and other production companies on the effects of psychosocial work and musculoskeletal disorders However, there is very little research conducted on the effects of psychosocial work and MSD construction workers' stress in Yobe state |Nigeria. It is based on this background that this research was conducted to avoid risk factors in construction industries.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to examine the effects of psychosocial work and musculoskeletal disorders on construction workers' stress in Yobe state Nigeria. | Specifically the study sought to:

1. Identify the effects of psychosocial work on construction workers' stress in construction industry in Yobe state, Nigeria.
2. Identify the common risk factors on workers' stress in construction industry in the study area.

Research Questions

It is in line with the stated objectives, that the following research questions were posed to guide the study:

1. What are the effects of psychosocial work on construction workers in construction industry in Yobe state Nigeria?
2. What are the common ergonomic risk factors on workers' stress in construction industry in the study area?

Research Hypotheses

Based on the purposes of this study, the following null hypotheses were formulated:

H0₁: There is no significant difference in the mean response of carpenters, iron binders, brick/block layers and concreters on the effects of psychosocial work on construction workers' stress in construction industry in Yobe state Nigeria.

H0₂: There is no significant difference in the mean response of carpenters, iron binders, brick/block layers and concreters on the common risk factors on workers' stress in construction industry in the study area.

Significance of the Study

This study when successfully completed, the result will be useful in the following ways: The results of this study will be useful to construction industry workers in providing them with useful knowledge and skills in getting rid of trauma effects that is accumulating as a result of repetitive actions. The result will also be useful to Medical Research Centers in Nigeria by providing current information on the method of identifying the possible causes of cumulative trauma disorders on workers in construction industry. The result will also be useful to ministry of labor and statistics that covers all data related to cumulative trauma disorder and other diseases related with trauma like vibration and noise induced hearing loss or pressure. Other beneficiaries will include wood cutters in wood industry who are always in a state of risk of psychosocial or trauma effects. Tiles and carpet layers will also find this result very useful being that it will provide them with an ergonomic safety measures against knee injury, plants and equipment operators like bulldozers, graders that experienced hand wrist problems will also find this result useful through helping them with adequate information on how to safeguard themselves from body injury that are traumatic.

The result of this study will also be useful to internally displaced persons (IDPs) centers/camps that are in the custody of Boko Haram insurgency effects where people were displaced from their towns and villages and got traumatic due to psychosocial effects that has affected them. Other form of internally displaced persons includes the victims of attacks by kidnappers and abductors where the effects of this episode are psychosocial because of loss of lives and properties by the victims. Construction industry workers most especially road construction are liable to risk of work stress, therefore, they will find the result of this study useful through enlighten them on psychological effect of work stress to be encountered at the construction site which includes sudden falls of objects with loud noise and its types. Studies on Construction industry workers paint a reasonably consistent picture of psychosocial factors as an amorphous array of characteristics of jobs, work environments and organizations that are hazardous for most work groups.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The design used for this study was a Cross-Sectional Survey Research Design employing occupational and environmental observations. A Cross-Sectional Research Design was defined as the type of Research Design where the researcher collects data at one point in time on current attitudes, beliefs, opinions or practices, (Simkus, 2023). This research design was considered suitable for this study because it measures the prevalence of diseases and describes the characteristics of population. It also examines a group of participants and depicts what already exist in the population without manipulating any variable or interfering with the environment.

This study was carried out in Yobe state which is located in North-East geo-political region of Nigeria, the region consists of six (6) states namely: Adamawa; Bauchi; Borno; Gombe; Taraba and Yobe state respectively which the study area is. The region lied between latitudes 6 degree 26” and 7 degree 12” east, and longitude 17 degree 22” and 20 degree 32” north on the globe and it covers a land mass of an area 104,639 square km. (www.researchgate.net). The communities of that area are mostly farmers, fisheries and traders. The population of this study was 90 construction industry workers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Research question one

What are the effects of psychosocial work on construction workers in construction industry in North-East Nigeria?

Table 4 showed mean responses and standard deviations of Carpenters, Bricklayers/Concreters, Iron Binders and Plumbers on effects of psychosocial work on construction workers in construction industry in North-East Nigeria. The table revealed that 9 items (items 1-5 and item 7-10) had their grand mean values ranging from 3.03 to 4.09 which are above the mean of 3.00 indicating that the 9 items were agreed by the respondents as effects of psychosocial work on construction workers. It can be deduced that one item (item 6) which had grand mean responses of 2.15 which is less than the mean point of 3.00 that was rated as less effects of psychosocial work on construction industry workers. The grand standard deviation values ranged from 0.85 to 1.08. Each of the values is low; indicating that the respondents are unanimous in their responses.

Table 1: Mean Rating on Effects of Psychosocial Work on Construction Workers in Construction Industry

S/N	Item	Carpenters		Bricklayers		Iron Binders		Plumbers		Grand		Remarks
		\bar{X}_C	SD _C	\bar{X}_B	SD _B	\bar{X}_I	SD _I	\bar{X}_P	SD _P	\bar{X}_G	SD _G	
1.	The effects of stress on construction workers is at:	3.27	1.17	3.25	0.11	3.07	0.88	3.0	0.80	3.17	0.99	Effect
2.	The effects of fatigue on construction workers is at:	3.65	0.84	3.94	0.99	3.73	0.63	3.7	0.81	3.77	0.86	Effect
3.	The effects of bullying on construction workers is at:	3.63	1.10	3.40	0.83	3.46	0.98	3.8	1.17	3.56	1.01	Effect
4.	Violence is one of the effects of psychosocial work on	3.14	1.03	3.36	0.99	3.27	0.87	3.2	1.05	3.25	0.99	Effect

	construction workers which appear at											
5.	The effect of aggression on construction workers is at:	3.68	1.04	3.42	1.0 3	3.56	0.8 7	3.8 8	1.1 6	3.6 0	1.0 3	Effect
6.	The effects of harassment on construction workers at construction industry is at	2.24	1.12	1.87	0.9 2	2.17	0.9 2	2.5 6	1.3 7	2.1 5	1.0 8	Less Effect
7.	Low job control on construction industry workers appears to be at:	3.90	0.91	3.73	0.8 2	3.83	0.8 0	3.9 1	0.7 8	3.8 3	0.8 5	Effect
8.	High job demands occurs in construction industry at where construction workers sustained high physical effort required to do the job	4.20	0.92	4.01	0.8 2	4.02	0.7 9	4.0 3	0.8 2	4.0 9	0.8 5	Effect
9.	Long periods of attention looking for infrequent events. For example, long-distance driving of heavy vehicles lead to psychosocial work	3.24	0.82	2.97	1.0 4	2.90	0.8 9	2.8 1	0.9 7	3.0 3	0.9 4	Effect
10.	Exposing construction workers to traumatic events like emergency	3.81	1.04	3.88	0.9 0	3.54	0.9 5	3.4 1	1.1 0	3.7 3	0.9 9	Effect

service lead to psychosocial work

Average	3.47	1.00	3.38	0.9	3.36	0.8	3.4	1.0	3.4	0.9	Effect
				2		6	4	0	2	6	

Source: Field Survey 2025

Research question two

What are the common ergonomic risk factors on workers’ stress in construction industry in the study area?

Table 2 showed the mean rating and standard deviations of Carpenters, Bricklayers/Concreters, Iron Binders and Plumbers on common ergonomic risk factors on workers’ stress in construction industry in North-East Nigeria. The result revealed that all the twelve items ranging from (items 11 to 22) had their mean values ranging from 3.51 to 4.18 with grand mean of 4.02. This indicated that respondents agreed that common risk factors is high on workers’ stress in construction industry. Thus, considering the standard deviation, SD ranged from 0.64 to 1.02 with a grand standard Deviation SD of 0.88. This indicated that the respondents agreed with the view that there is no significant difference in the mean response of the subjects on the common risk factors on workers’ stress in construction industry in North-East Nigeria.

Table 5: Mean Rating on Common Risk Factors on Workers’ Stress in Construction Industry

S/N	Item	Carpenters		Bricklayers		Iron Binders		Plumbers		Grand		Remark
		\bar{X}_C	SD_C	\bar{X}_B	SD_B	\bar{X}_I	SD_I	\bar{X}_P	SD_P	\bar{X}_G	SD_G	
11.	The possibility of occurrence of low job control in construction industry as common ergonomic risk factor on workers’ stress is:	4.02	0.89	4.03	0.74	4.07	0.61	4.22	1.16	4.06	0.84	Common
12.	High job demands in construction industry is another common ergonomic risk	3.73	1.17	3.96	0.79	4.05	0.63	3.97	0.82	3.89	0.93	Common

	factor on workers' stress which happen as:											
13.	Low job demands in construction industry is another common ergonomic risk factor on workers' stress which happen as:	4.11	0.98	3.87	0.91	3.95	0.77	4.38	0.98	4.04	0.93	Common
14.	The rate of Poor support as common ergonomic risk factor on workers' stress is in construction industry	4.14	0.96	3.91	0.91	4.00	0.74	4.41	0.95	4.08	0.91	Common
15.	There is poor workplace relationship between the construction workers and the job demands in safe working environment, and it is happening at:	4.17	0.94	3.96	0.83	4.15	0.57	4.25	1.14	4.11	0.89	Common
16.	Poor organizational justice that occurred as common ergonomic risk factor on workers' stress which is happening in construction	4.18	0.84	4.12	0.76	4.20	0.51	4.31	1.06	4.18	0.79	Common

	industry											
17.	Another common ergonomic risk factor on workers' stress is low recognition and it occurred as in construction industry	4.06	0.92	3.92	0.89	4.05	0.71	4.34	0.94	4.05	0.88	Common
18.	The rate of occurrence of low reward as common ergonomic risk factor on workers' stress is in construction industry	4.14	0.88	4.27	0.64	3.95	0.74	4.38	0.98	4.18	0.81	Common
19.	Low role clarity is also a common ergonomic risk factor on workers' stress which is on construction industry workers	4.13	0.97	4.05	0.87	3.85	0.82	4.53	0.84	4.11	0.91	Common
20.	Poor environmental condition identified as common ergonomic risk factor that lead to injury is in construction industry	4.06	1.01	4.00	0.92	3.90	0.83	4.31	0.99	4.05	0.95	Common
21.	Another common ergonomic risk factor on workers' stress	3.93	1.07	3.84	0.99	3.66	0.88	4.28	1.05	3.90	1.02	Common

which affect construction industry workers is working in isolation.

22.	Work related stress in construction industry, and identified as common ergonomic risk factor on workers' stress that affect workers in construction industry	3.60	0.62	3.64	0.67	3.49	0.60	3.47	0.67	3.57	0.64	Common
Average		4.02	0.94	3.96	0.83	3.94	0.70	4.24	0.96	4.02	0.88	Common

Source: Field Survey 2025

Testing Null Hypothesis

Null hypothesis one

There is no significant difference in the mean response of carpenters, iron binders, brick/block layers and plumbers on the effects of psychosocial work on construction workers in construction industries in Yobe state, Nigeria.

Table 1 presented the result of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) which shows the statistical result of mean difference among carpenters, bricklayers/concreters, iron binders and plumbers on the effects of psychosocial work on construction workers. The result shows F-calculated value of 0.751 and a p-value of 0.523. The p-value is greater than 0.05 level of significant ($p > .05$). This shows that the null hypothesis is therefore accepted, meaning there is no significant difference among the mean responses of carpenters, bricklayers/concreters, iron binders and plumbers on the effects of psychosocial work on construction workers.

Table 1: ANOVA test of Significant Difference among Respondents on the Effects of Psychosocial Work on Construction Workers

Source of Variance	Sum of Square	Degree of Freedom (df)	Mean Square (MS)	F	P-value	Level of Significant	Remark
Between Groups	49.635	3	16.545	.751	.523	.05	Not Significant

Within Groups	5070.181	230	22.044
Total	5119.816	233	

Source: Field Survey 2025

Null hypothesis two

There is no significant difference among the mean responses of carpenters, bricklayers/concreters, iron binders and plumbers on the common risk factors on workers' stress in construction industry.

Table 2 presents the result of ANOVA which shows the statistical result of mean difference among carpenters, bricklayers/concreters, iron binders and plumbers on the common risk factors on workers' stress in construction industry in the study area. The result shows F-calculated value of .1.332 and a p-value of .265. This, appears to be greater than 0.05 level of significant ($p > .05$). This showed that the null hypothesis is therefore considered accepted, that there is no significant difference among the mean responses of carpenters, bricklayers/concreters, iron binders and plumbers on the common risk factors on workers' stress in construction industry.

Table 2: ANOVA test of Significant Difference among Respondents on the Common Risk Factors on Workers' Stress in Construction Industry

Source of Variance	Sum of Square	Degree of Freedom (df)	Mean Square (MS)	F	P-value	Level of Significant	Remark
Between Groups	286.252	3	95.417	1.332	.265	.05	Not Significant
Within Groups	16478.192	230	71.644				
Total	16764.444	233					

Source: Field Survey 2025

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the research on null hypothesis one revealed that there is effects of psychosocial work on construction workers' stress in construction industry. Being that it has a grand mean of 3.42 and a standard deviation of 0.96. This is in line with the work of Gale, Andrew, Skitmore, and Martin, (2018) who conducted a study on the attitudes of women towards the United Kingdom (UK) construction industry. The major findings of these two studies were described which suggest that females generally see construction as a form of cottage industry. As a result, a recommendation was made for increase in publicity and education about the construction industry and its professional occupations.

The intention was to identify empirically the major relevant variables associated with the industry's image, in terms of dependent variables such as respondents' age, gender, education,

residence, occupation, and knowledge, experience and interest in the industry, and in terms of independent variables such as the quality and quantity.

Finding of the null hypothesis two indicated that ergonomic risk factors on workers' stress in construction industry was identified as most common since it has a grand mean of 4.02 and a standard deviation of 0.88. This had corroborated with the work of Prel-du (2024). who conducted a study on the factors influencing construction ergonomic performance in India, the study made use of questionnaire-based survey in gathering the primary data for ergonomic design and analysis of the man-machine handling task MMH / jobs at construction site, The study addressed a number of relevant five research issues related to the workers involved in man machine interaction at the construction site. Data collected through the survey assessed the risk factors associated with various MMH activities for which biomechanical, physiological and physical evaluation are necessary. The result revealed that based on the responses, the contribution of each of the factors influencing construction ergonomic performance were examined and the ranking of the attributes in terms of their criticality as perceived by the respondents was found by Relative Importance Index (RII) is as follows: $A \times N$ (0 Less than or equal to R II less than or equal to 1).

When the data was analyzed, it was observed that the risk of musculoskeletal injury/ disorder appeared to be highest among mason helpers as compared to other occupations because they suffer from pain in almost the joints and the risk factors are also critical and versatile in nature of construction-related MMH activities and highly correlated to the causes of MSDs, and that apart from masons and masons helpers, carpenters also suffer from pain that cause a number of MSDs among them because they are also highly involved in MMH activities.. It was also found from the result of the study that 40 % of the masons and carpenters were between the age groups of 25- 34 years and 3% are less than 25 years. The result of the study also revealed that 40% of the masons workers are below 25 years of age and most of them are between 25 to 34 years of age.

Conclusion

This research shows in general terms, that construction industry workers based on the findings of this study, usually experienced some common hazards based on the nature of their work thereby causing cumulative trauma disorder. Some common hazards identified includes awkward postures, repetitive work, forceful exertions stress and vibrations. Other aspects of hazards experienced are ergonomic risk which vary based on the nature of the work and work station and these includes occurrence of low-job control, high job demands, poor supports and poor work place, low recognition and poor environmental condition.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Construction industry workers should avoid any anti-social vices that will cause effects of psychosocial work like aggression and harassment or low job control that will affect workers in construction industry.
- ii. Construction industry workers should avoid any act of risk such as ergonomic risk like high job demands, uncomfortable static position, contact stress of muscles and tendons and extreme temperature condition should be avoided to prevent the development of ergonomic risks on construction industry workers.

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